

Title: Sacrifice Container

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

This work is a sound installation using a large woofer. The "sacrifice" is made by having one person lie on top of the woofer and surrounding it for viewing. The audience is enveloped in the story by viewing a lone person lying on top of a large speaker, as if offering a sacrifice in a ritualistic way, thereby drawing the audience members into the narrative. In addition, the very large bass, consisting of woofers, gives a sense of presence and eeriness. The sound flowing from here is based on the traditional folk tales of "Bon-Bon Shark" that remains in the Japanese town of Manazuru and composed as a Soundscape composition. The story is about a couple sharks who are killed by a bell dropped from a boat by a sailor, and sacrifices are made to these sharks.

Fig. 1. "Sacrifice Container" at 2022.

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The aim of this study is to reproduce "Yōkai" supernatural creatures, through sound in order to allow the audience to relive the experiences of those who have encountered Yōkai.

In Japanese folklore, "Yōkai" refers to supernatural creatures like spirits, monsters, and demons. These creatures can take many forms, including shape-shifting animals, ghosts, and mischievous spirits.

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Fig. 2. Yōkai images[1]

While some Yōkai are well-known for their unique appearance, others are only known for their sounds. This is because the idea of Yōkai often comes from the experience of feeling a presence in darkness where vision is deprived. However, today, the focus on Yōkai as characters is causing the actual folklore and beliefs to be forgotten.

The theme of this work is "Bon-Bon Shark," a sound-only Yōkai. Here is an English translation of the story.

“ Once upon a time, there was a couple of sharks who lived here and protected their young by driving away fishing boats. One day, a ship with three Buddhist bells passed by from the upper area. The male shark attacked the ship, but the ship's captain dropped one of the bells to make the ship lighter. The male shark was sealed and sank because of the dropped bell. The female shark, who also attacked the ship to avenge her husband, was also sealed and sank. After that, whenever the sea near this area was passed by, the sound of a bell ringing could be heard from the seabed. This was because the young sharks were trying to free their parents by striking the bell with their powerful tails. The sound of the ringing bell is still heard from the waves to this day. The area sharks became known as the "bon-bon shark" because of the ringing bell. “

Fig. 3. Manazuru (License Free Photos)

I went to Manazuru and did field recording, and composed based on those sounds.

Fig. 3. Field recording at night (using ZOOM H3-VR Audio Recorder)

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

Technical equipment Provided by artist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PC • Woofer • Speakers • Speaker stands • Audio Interface • Cables
Equipment requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approx. 600W
Volume level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 60~70db
Performance time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approx. 5~10 minutes per session
Space requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum 4m² • A dimly lit space
Set-up time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1day

Fig. 4. External dimensions of woofer unit (Transport to the venue) [2]

Fig. 5. Enclosure Size. Material is MDF. Assembled on site.[2]

Fig. 6. Device to lie on top of the woofer.
Assembled on site if difficult to transport.

4. MEDIA LINK

- Video (short ver.) : https://youtu.be/c9MUSZ2_4JY
A video of my performance at an exhibition on campus.

ETHICAL STANDARDS

In this research and work, ethical standards are followed. No monetary gain or profit is aimed for in this study. To contribute to the prosperity of Japanese culture and cultural exchange between Japan and other countries. Also, the people participating in the work have obtained prior consent. Beforehand, the explanation is given that there will be low FREQUENCY and LOUD volume performances. It is explained that some people may feel nausea, headache, tinnitus, etc. due to large subwoofers. Particularly for those who wish to experience sleeping on the subwoofers, we will take care to ensure that they can be attended immediately if they feel unwell during the experience.

REFERENCES

- [1] International Research Center for Japanese Studies Kaiyodo/Yokai Image Database
<https://www.nichibun.ac.jp/YoukaiGazouMenu/>
- [2] FW800HS | Fostex, *Fostex*. <https://www.fostex.jp/products/fw800hs/>